

Description of the certification process for biochar-based carbon sinks ¹

Nikolas Hagemann^{1,2,3}

¹Agroscope, Reckenholzstrasse 191, 8046 Zurich, Switzerland

²Ithaka Institut, Ancienne Eglise 9, 1974 Arbaz, Switzerland

³Ithaka Institut, Altmutterweg 21, 63773 Goldbach, Germany

The following text describes how a C-sink certification based on a biochar application is carried out. The procedures are based on the European Biochar Certificate (EBC) C-sink certificate guidelines, version 2.1 of Feb. 01st, 2021. However, they are also exemplary for comparable regulations and certifications and do not claim to be exhaustive. Most standards require a certification of the biochar (the physical product) according to the EBC (EBC Guidelines for sustainable production of biochar, version 10.3 of Apr. 5th, 2023). For a comprehensive and detailed description, reading the latest version of the guidelines, available at www.european-biochar.org or www.carbon-standards.com, is recommended.

Carbon footprint of biochar production

When biochar is produced from biomass (e.g., from landscaping wood) via pyrolysis, the producer is certified according to the European Biochar Certificate or the World Biochar Certificate (www.european-biochar.org). The certification process includes an on-site audit and data collection necessary to calculate biochar production's carbon expenditures (i.e., carbon footprint) in kilograms of CO₂e emitted per ton of biochar (dry matter). For example, this includes the amount of electricity and fuels needed for all operations, which includes biomass transportation to the pyrolysis unit, biomass conditioning (milling, drying, etc.), conveyors, and other auxiliary equipment of the pyrolysis unit and for (pre-)heating the pyrolysis reactor. When primary biomass is used, additional emissions would be accounted for, for example, from fertilization and land management during biomass production. However, landscaping wood is considered a secondary biomass; only emissions starting with the biomass collection are included. Concerning the emissions of the pyrolysis plant, the methane emissions are recorded. As direct methane measurements at all individual plants are too expensive, measurements from reference plants of the same model using comparable feedstock are used (certification of pyrolysis plants).

¹ Please cite as: Hagemann, Nikolas: Description of the certification process for biochar-based carbon sinks. Ithaka Institute, Arbaz, Switzerland, 2024. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10580112](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10580112)

Foundation Ithaka Institute

An exemplary pyrolysis plant produced 1000 t biochar within a batch². It caused the emission of 50 t CO_{2e} for biomass transportation, 200 t CO_{2e} for its operation (electricity, fuel), and methane equivalent to 50 t CO_{2e}, which sums up to 300 t CO_{2e}. To account for further emissions, another 10% is added as a margin of safety, resulting in 330 t CO_{2e} per batch or 0.33 t CO_{2e} t⁻¹ biochar.

All emissions must be compensated with a high-quality carbon sink certificate to achieve climate-neutral production. The IDs of the certificates used for compensation are linked to the production batch to ensure transparency of the compensation.

Carbon sink potential

A representative sample from each batch of biochar is taken and analyzed, among others, for its organic carbon and hydrogen content. The amount of organic carbon in a ton of biochar (dry matter) is called the carbon sink potential (unit: t t⁻¹ CO_{2e}), given that all emissions caused by its productions are offset. In our example, the biochar contains 75% organic carbon (0.75 kg C t⁻¹).

Tracking of biochar, biochar C sink registration

Each packaging unit of biochar receives a unique ID that allows the tracking of the biochar from its producer via traders and processors to the farmer who will apply it in his field. For this purpose, each ID is registered in a tracking system, also referred to as digital monitoring, reporting, and verification (dMRV) system. This allows the calculation of transport and processing emissions and the confirmation of the application of the biochar to the soil. Once applied to the soil, a rapid oxidation of the biochar is impossible. The ID of the biochar and the field location (GPS coordinates and/or registration number on the official land register) are used to create an entry in the C sink register. The landowner becomes the owner of the C-sink, but they may sell the rights to use the C-sink's climate effect. Once the registered C-sink certificate is used, e.g., for compensation for a flight, the C-sink certificate is marked as retired in the register.

Example

A farmer purchased 3 t of biochar with 33% moisture content, i.e., 2 t of dry matter in biochar, that was applied to his field prior to plowing the winter greening to ensure the incorporation of the biochar. Farmer confirms this in the dMRV app, which has permission to use his

² A batch is the amount of biochar produced within a maximum of 365 days under constant pyrolysis conditions, and from a constant and homogeneous feedstock.

geolocation and the map outlining the plot to which the biochar was applied (1 ha). Then, a C-sink certificate is created and registered with $2 \text{ t} * 0.75 \text{ t t}^{-1} \text{ Corg} * 44.01/12.011 = 5.50 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e}$, of which 75% (4.13 t CO₂e.) are considered to be persistent beyond 1000 years (Schmidt et al., 2022). As transportation of the biochar from the pyrolysis facility to the field caused a total of 50 kg CO₂e emissions, the farmer uses his newly created C-sink to compensate for these emissions and the respective share of production emissions accounting for $(2 \text{ t} * 0.33 \text{ t t}^{-1} \text{ CO}_2\text{e} \Rightarrow) 0.66 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e}$. The farmer retires, thus, $(0.05 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e} + 0.66 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e} \Rightarrow) 0.71 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e}$ from the persistent part of the registered C-sink and may sell the remaining $(4.13 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e} - 0.71 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e} \Rightarrow) 3.42 \text{ t CO}_2\text{e}$ on the voluntary market for emission compensation. 1.37 t CO₂e are stored temporarily in the semi-persistent carbon pool of the biochar (Schmidt et al., 2022).